

At first, highest grain yield of rice and wheat during kharif was obtained with T5 (100% NPK through fertilizer). The treatments T7 (75% NPK + 25% N [FYM]), T9 (75% NPK + 25% N [straw]), and T11 (75% NPK + 25% N [GM]) gave higher rice yields than T6 (50% NPK + 50% N [FYM]), T8 (50% NPK + 50% N [straw]), and T10 (50% NPK + 50% N [GM]). During rabi, T6, T8, and T10 produced higher wheat yield than T7, T9, and T10, a result that may be attributed to 25% less NPK. The control recorded the lowest yield, and declined over the years. In later years, T6 and T10 have shown the highest response over the control, indicating that a 50% NPK saving could be achieved by continuous application of FYM or GM during kharif. Treatments T7 and T11 showed a 25% NPK saving. Total mean

productivity over the years in treatments T6 and T10 was comparable with that of T5.

Available N, P, and K (Table 2) decreased over the control after conventional treatment. Minimum depletion of N was observed in treatment T7 during kharif followed by T5 (100% NPK through chemical fertilizers in both seasons), T11, and T10.

Available P also decreased over the years, except for T5, where an appreciable buildup was observed. Available K content decreased in all treatments and maximum depletion was observed in the control.

These results suggest that combined use of organic and inorganic fertilizers can sustain soil fertility and grain yields in rice - wheat cropping systems. ■

Table 2. Effect of integrated nutrient supply on soil fertility changes under rice - wheat cropping system. Jammu, India, 1992-93.

Treatment no. ^a	Available nutrients (kg ha ⁻¹) after 8 yr					
	1992 kharif			1992-93 rabi		
	N	P	K	N	P	K
T1	179.2	5.42	87.0	162.0	5.10	82.5
T2	224.0	8.10	94.0	213.7	7.40	91.0
T3	251.0	8.80	94.5	247.5	8.25	91.0
T4	245.7	11.90	88.2	237.5	10.60	91.0
T5	310.2	20.40	101.4	301.0	17.90	97.4
T6	296.5	12.40	97.4	287.5	12.00	97.4
T7	327.0	16.80	102.0	310.5	15.25	97.4
T8	277.0	11.10	102.0	266.5	10.60	97.4
T9	278.0	11.10	98.5	271.1	10.85	98.5
T10	296.5	11.10	98.5	292.3	10.60	97.4
T11	301.0	10.90	87.2	292.3	10.60	83.5
T12	189.5	6.90	76.5	183.0	6.70	72.2
Initial	456.0	13.80	154.00			

^a See Table 1 for details.

Crop management

Effect of foliage pruning on performance of rice under semi-deep water situations (50-100 cm)

A. Ghosh and A. R. Sharma, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, Orissa 753006, India

We studied the response of rice yield to foliage pruning under excess water (>50 cm) at Cuttack during 1995 wet season using Panidhan (semi-tall, 180 d) and LPR312 (tall, 170 d) varieties. They were direct-sown in puddled soil the first week of June at 400 seeds m⁻¹ in 20-cm row spacings with basal fertilizers at 40 kg N ha⁻¹, 17.6 kg P ha⁻¹, and 33.2 kg K ha⁻¹. Foliage was pruned above the joint (collar) of the topmost leaf once or twice at 80, 100, and 120 d after germination (DAG). A split-plot design was used, data analyzed by standard analysis of variance, and treatment means were compared at the 5% level.

Crops emerged the second week of June, and by the first part of July, water level was 80 cm deep, fluctuating between 35 and 60 cm during crop growth period and receding gradually by crop maturity in mid-December.

Foliage pruning influenced plant growth (Table 1). Vertical growth picked up faster after first and second pruning but slowed down after third pruning. LPR312 produced more foliage than did Panidhan. Foliage taken at different times and frequencies differed from one another. Pruning at later growth stages gave more foliage than that at early stages. Interaction

between pruning and variety was not significant. However, LPR312 at delayed pruning gave more foliage than Panidhan. Foliage pruning was found detrimental to panicle growth and development, especially at later growth stages (Table 2). Panicle sterility was 2-3% higher with delayed pruning and two prunings compared with no pruning. Yield response also declined.

Table 1. Plant height and foliage yield of rice varieties at different times and number of leaf prunings.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)			Foliage yield (t ha ⁻¹)		
	80 DAG ^a	100 DAG	120 DAG	Maturity	Fresh	Dry
<i>Variety</i>						
Panidhan	119	129	146	150	4.0	1.3
LPR312	116	133	157	164	4.9	1.6
CD (5%)	ns	ns	ns	ns	1.3	0.4
<i>Pruning</i>						
No pruning	116	137	166	174	-	-
One pruning at						
80 DAG	118	136	163	167	2.9	0.7
100 DAG	121	135	154	160	3.4	0.8
120 DAG	116	124	149	157	4.3	1.4
Two prunings at						
80 + 100 DAG	116	124	147	161	5.7	1.6
100 + 120 DAG	117	134	154	156	7.0	2.4
80 + 120 DAG	118	125	141	155	6.1	2.0
CD (5%)	ns	7.7	10.5	9.4	1.0	0.3

^aDAG - days after germination.

Table 2. Effect of leaf pruning on yield and yield components of rice. Cuttack, India, 1995.

Treatment	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Panicle weight (g)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Panicle sterility (%)
<i>Variety</i>					
Panidhan	141	2.61	2.3	7.9	8.4
LPR312	151	2.55	2.3	7.2	8.2
CD (5%)	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
<i>Pruning</i>					
No pruning	160	2.73	2.6	10.2	5.5
<i>One pruning at</i>					
80 DAG	148	2.60	2.5	9.6	6.5
100 DAG	138	2.84	2.5	8.6	7.3
120 DAG	143	2.21	2.0	8.6	8.5
<i>Two prunings at</i>					
80 + 100 DAG	143	2.36	2.3	7.7	8.3
100 + 120 DAG	133	2.23	2.0	7.6	8.7
80 + 120 DAG	136	2.16	1.9	7.1	8.3
CD(5%)	12	ns	0.4	1.6	1.1

Early pruning produced more grain yield than delayed pruning. In general, foliage pruning up to 100 DAG produced grain yield comparable with that of no pruning, but pruning thereafter reduced grain yield.

Significant reduction was also found in straw yield at maturity. It was more pronounced when foliage was removed twice. One early pruning (80 DAG) had no adverse effect on straw yield. Pruning delayed after 80 DAG or

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twice at either of the two growth stages reduced straw yield by 19-21% and 33-44% respectively, compared with no pruning.

The results suggest that foliage pruning of tall and long-duration rice variety may be used to supplement cattle rations in lowland areas lacking fodder in wet season. However, foliage should be removed at early growth stages, preferably 35-40 d before flowering, in order not to adversely affect grain yield. ■

Effect of seed rate, seed density, and nitrogen fertilizer on performance of flood-prone lowland rice

A. Ghosh and A.R. Sharma; Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 75300, India

We conducted two experiments during 1994 at Cuttack, India in adjoining fields. In the first, seeds of varying densities were sown at different rates using a common basal dose of 40 kg N ha⁻¹. Nine treatment combinations were arranged in a factorial randomized complete block design with three replications. In experiment 2, only low- and high-density seeds were grown at 400 and 600 seeds m⁻² using 0 and 40 kg N ha⁻¹. Sixteen treatment combinations were arranged in a split-plot design with three replications, keeping submergence levels in main plots and combinations of seed rate, seed density, and N fertilizer in sub-plots.

Rain began 10 d after sowing, with 10.4, 4.8, and 0.8 mm falling at 2-d

Table 1. Growth and yield of rice as influenced by seed rate and seed density in the flood-prone lowlands of Cuttack, India, during 1994 (Experiment 1).^a

Treatment	Seedling emergence (%)	Plant height at maturity (cm)	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Panicle weight (g)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)
<i>20 seeds m⁻²</i>						
19.4 mg	30.4	132	75	2.95	2.0	5.6
21.2 mg	32.2	138	107	3.22	2.7	6.0
22.9 mg	33.1	139	115	3.20	2.9	6.7
<i>40 seeds m⁻²</i>						
19.4 mg	30.4	132	93	2.75	2.3	7.8
21.2 mg	32.7	138	116	2.80	2.7	8.3
22.9 mg	33.5	138	122	2.88	2.8	8.7
<i>600 seeds m⁻²</i>						
19.4 mg	30.3	133	106	2.75	2.5	7.9
21.2 mg	32.6	135	127	2.74	2.8	8.6
22.9 mg	34.0	138	121	2.85	2.8	8.2
Mean effects						
<i>Seed rate (m²)</i>						
200	31.9	136	99	3.12	2.5	6.1
400	32.2	136	110	2.81	2.6	8.3
600	32.3	135	118	2.78	2.7	8.2
<i>Seed density (mg)</i>						
19.4	30.4	132	91	2.82	2.3	7.1
21.2	32.5	138	117	2.92	2.7	7.6
22.9	33.5	137	119	2.98	2.8	7.9
CD (P=0.05)						
Seed rate	ns	ns	ns	0.25	ns	0.83
Seed density	ns	3	ns	ns	0.2	ns
Interaction	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.4	ns

^a Gayatri, a semidwarf, long-duration, photoperiod-sensitive, relatively flood-tolerant variety, was used. Crop was direct-sown on 25 May after premonsoon showers at a row spacing of 20 cm using a common basal dose of 8.7 kg P ha⁻¹ and 16.7 kg K ha⁻¹. Seeds of varying grades were obtained by repeated screening of thoroughly cleaned seeds in a saline solution (sp. gr., 1.2; 300 g common salt L⁻¹ of water).